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Deliverable 5.3

Integrated assessment of resilience across forest systems and forest-wood value chains

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.3 from Task 5.2 focuses on constructing an integrated forest ecosystem and forest value-chain resilience assessment, utilising insights from WP1's framework and derived indicators. The primary objective is to employ multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) based on pairwise comparisons, assessing key resilience challenges and measures across forest systems and value chains, based on expert evaluation. This process involves active engagement with forest owners, forest-based industry representatives, and researchers/interest group representatives or other experts, facilitating the understanding of diverse perspectives. Pairwise comparisons were chosen as a method to systematically evaluate the relative importance of resilience challenges and measures among these different expert groups. Thus, our approach enables an integrated exploration of preferences between different expert perspectives on the resilience of forest ecosystems and wood-based value chains. The MCDA results thus provide valuable insights into the perceived effectiveness of various resilience-related measures and highlight similarities and differences in opinions among expert groups of forest owners, forest-based industry representatives, and forest-based researchers/NGOs. These findings facilitate the identification of areas of trade-offs in addressing resilience challenges through specific measures within forest ecosystems and the wood value chain.

The deliverable serves as a preview of our initial case study results from Finland, to be complemented by two additional case study regions, namely Bavaria and Galicia. This comparative approach allows insights into the regional-specific relative importance of resilience challenges and the evaluation of measures according to expert groups.

Keywords

Resilience Assessment, Resilience Measures, MCDA, Pairwise Comparisons

2. Introduction

RESONATE aims to generate the needed knowledge and practices for making European forests, the services they provide, and related economic activities more resilient to future climate change and disturbances. To this extent, WP 5 provides a synthesising analysis of the results derived from previous work packages and develops guidance and recommendations for policy and practice. More precisely, an integrated forest and value-chain resilience assessment to improve policy coherence and forest value chain adaptability regarding identified key resilience challenges within forest system and forest value chains across European regions is being created (T5.1). An integrated understanding based on identified current and future hotspots of natural disturbances in Europe is created and contrasted with forest-based value chains which have adapted their business models according to resilience challenges (T5.2). Furthermore, in co-creation with decision-makers, a comprehensive European level understanding on how to balance resilience challenges across societal demands and in different parts of the social-ecological systems is being achieved (T5.3). Finally, a synthesis and recommendations for improved resilience management for policy and other decision-makers is being prepared (T5.4).

In line with these efforts, this deliverable (D.5.3) provides a preliminary assessment of key resilience measures including their given priorities along forest systems and forest value chains. It applies a multi-criteria method and provides the necessary information for better management of resilience-related trade-offs. This interim report is accomplished by identifying the principal determinants for future forest-wood value chain resilience. The work used indicators identified in the Resilience Dashboard (D1.5) as the basis for resilience measures to be analysed. This deliverable will show results from the assessment of key resilience challenges and measures according to Finnish forest value chain experts and serves as a showcase of the multi-criteria method deployed. The work will further include two more case study regions, namely Galicia and Bavaria, which will allow for a detailed comparison of the assessment of resilience challenges and measures in different regions across expert groups. This work will be further elaborated and synthesized in D5.5.

2.1 Research gap

Forest ecosystems are crucial for preserving biodiversity and providing various ecological, social, and economic services. However, they face numerous challenges that test their adaptability. Climate change is altering the distribution of tree species and increasing the frequency and severity of environmental disturbances like wildfires and insect outbreaks (Schelhaas et al., 2003; Thuiller et al., 2011). These disturbances cause significant ecological

and economic damage. Additionally, forests, with their long lifespan, are vulnerable to both short- and long-term environmental disruptions (Alberto et al., 2013). Climate-driven stressors and disturbances compromise forests' ability to act as carbon sinks, affecting climate mitigation efforts (Anderegg et al., 2020). Forests provide multiple goods and services for the society including e.g. wood- and non-wood products, climate regulation, recreational services and habitat for great variety of species. However, these demands are evolving due to changing forest owner objectives, policies, and market dynamics (Winkel et al., 2022). Balancing these demands while maintaining forest ecosystem health requires careful consideration of potential trade-offs and synergies (Dallimer et al., 2015; Pingoud et al., 2018). Finally, recognising the threat of irreversible biodiversity loss, EU policies like the Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020) prioritise the preservation of forest ecosystems as part of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019).

In this context, following Hurtado et al. (2022) and Biggs et al. (2015), we understand resilience as the capacity of the social-ecological system (SES) to reorganise, adapt and continuously provide ecosystem services in the face of unexpected shocks as well as under gradual, ongoing changes such as climate change and the challenges described above.

There is a growing body of literature dedicated to the modeling and assessment of empirical indicators related to resilience (Albrich et al., 2020; Folke, 2016) as well as the assessment of trade-offs and synergies between competing interests (Pingoud et al., 2018; Thrippleton et al., 2021). However, the importance, or opinion of the implementation order, of different goals vary depending on the region-specific circumstances as well as the personal background of the expert who is asked. Given the goals of enhancing the resilience of forests and associated value chains and considering the social-ecological forest system as adaptive and in need of adaptation, the perspectives of managers should be incorporated, because they are integral components of this system. The experts operating in different parts of the wood- based value chain may not share consensus of the priority measures regarding resilience, although their opinions are mutually important.

In recent decades, there has been a rising call for the involvement of experts like local inhabitants in the decision-making process within the context of forest planning and management. Participatory decision-making techniques aim to aid in showing differences and reaching consensus among diverse experts and fostering transparent and effective outcomes (Baudry et al., 2018). Participation is undertaken for various reasons and motives. The substantive perspective emphasizes its role in producing better societal outcomes. From this viewpoint, participation improves the understanding of complex decision problems by

incorporating multiple perspectives, making it a useful tool to reflect the knowledge and viewpoints of various experts.

Our study aspires to bridge the existing gap between identified forest resilience-improving measures and the expert opinions of their importance in different regions in the EU. To this purpose, we use multi-criteria assessment distributed for an expert panel, consisting of forest-based industry representatives, forest owners and forest bioeconomy or ecology researchers, interest group or other similar experts (referred from now on generally as NGOs), starting with the case of Finland.

2.2 Research objective

By implementing a multi criteria decision-making method based on expert judgment of four general forest-value chain resilience challenges identified in RESONATE project (i. biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems, ii.) tree species suitability to adapt climate change, iii) increased risk of forest disturbances and associated damages (increased risk if forest damages), and iv) change in societal demand, which in our case relates to an increase in raw material remand for the needs of bioeconomy, we aim to (1) identify the relative priority of resilience challenges and 2) identify the relative priority of different resilience measures responding to identified challenges, according to different expert groups, and (3) compare expert group-specific differences in opinions. Following a participatory decision-making process based on pairwise comparisons of resilience challenges and measures, we strive to add to the discourse on how to increase the resilience of forest ecosystems and forest-based value chains (resilience of what?) to the abovementioned resilience challenges of changing tree species suitability, increased risk of natural disturbances, changes in societal demands of ecosystem goods and services and biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems (resilience to what?) and identify the relative importance of resilience measures (Carpenter et al., 2001). The benefit of using pairwise comparison is to determine the priority order of resilience measures, which is not typically clear in general importance rankings in which all measures are perceived as having equal importance. In other words, when studying the prioritization order and differences in opinions, it is more useful to ask, “how much more important challenge x is compared to challenge y” than “how important”, since there is a higher risk of experts considering all the challenges important without clear distinction between them. The pairwise comparison results also allow to explore possible interlinkages between resilience challenges and -measures, that are found in the previous studies.

We perform the analysis in different countries but in this report we focus on the results of the first case study country, Finland. In the further steps we aim to compare the results between different countries, namely Galicia (Spain) and Bavaria (Germany).

Preliminary research questions:

- 1) Are the expert opinions internally consistent regarding resilience challenges and measures within the pre-set expert groups; Forest-based industry representatives, Forest owners and forest researchers/NGOs.
- 2) Are there differences in the expert opinions between pre-set groups?
- 3) Which resilience challenges and measures are ranked the highest/lowest among different pre-set groups?
- 4) Are there potential trade-offs (potentially contradicting resilience measures) along the value chain regarding different opinions of the prioritisation?

Our primary objective is to facilitate the prioritisation of concrete resilience measures and challenges. By doing so, we aim to uncover the value positions and associated trade-offs prevalent among different expert groups along the value chain. This will provide a foundation for the development of regionally specific management and policy options.

3. Methods and Data

3.1 Methodological approach

3.1.1 Participatory decision making

To gain insights in group-specific commonalities and differences, we use participatory decision-making, which is predicated on the principle of involving relevant experts in the decision-making process, ensuring that their perspectives are considered (Yaffee & Wondolleck, 2000). In complex decision-making environments like social-ecological resilience where a multitude of challenges and possible measures are present, as well as historical/cultural context and group interests, participation of experts provides tools to prioritise resilience challenges and measures and uncover underlying trade-offs along the value chain.

We first specified four region-specific resilience challenges based on four criteria defined within RESONATE: i) Biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems, ii) Changing raw material demand for the society, iii) Increased risk of forest disturbances and iv) Tree species suitability to adapt climate change. Measures to respond to these resilience challenges were identified by utilising modelling study indicators (resilience affecting parameters, here measures) from the RESONATE case study work. The list of measures was restricted to ones that are not ambiguous and can be easily understood in a quantitative manner. Since these measures are expected to favour resilience and are suitable to be implemented, they correspond to resilience predictors as proposed in the ORF developed in WP1 (Lloret et al., 2023).

Potential resilience measures were defined as:

- Increasing the share of mixed species forests
- Tightening the criteria for forest certificates
- Increasing the density of road network
- Increasing people employed within forest value chains
- Increasing share of forest area under protection
- Increasing share of uneven-aged forests
- Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used
- Increase in felling volume

3.1.2 Pairwise comparison method

Pairwise comparison, originally proposed by Thurstone (1927), is frequently used in multi-criteria decision methods, like the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 2001). Pairwise comparison uses a cardinal ranking of alternatives in pairs, indicating the relative priority of these options in a structured manner. It offers the advantage of seeing the intensity of preference for alternatives over ordinal ranking methods. With pairwise comparisons, each expert has the option to express the intensity or importance that they give to one alternative - with respect to another (Mendoza & Prabhu, 2000). In our case the alternatives corresponded to the importance of the different pairs of resilience challenges and the suitability of resilience measures. In this study setting, we focused on the forest-value chain in whole Finland and presented ready resilience challenge alternatives for the experts.

The resilience measures in the survey were mainly focused on forest ecosystem and less on production stages and end-use markets of wood products in the technosphere (i.e. increasing demand to substitute fossil products). One reason was to focus on measures that are easily understood. If more market-oriented measures were included, it would have required recruiting a larger set of different type of experts, who on the other hand could have had less knowledge about forest management and state of Finnish forests in general. Despite the measures focusing more on forest ecosystem resilience, the respondents had to consider the whole value chain instead of only a part of the value chain (i.e. forest value chain vs forest stand, whole country vs singular region or municipality) when responding and this was emphasised in the cover letter as well as in the survey introducing the study setting. Since the resilience perception largely depends on the expert's personal background and values, we were first asking them to compare the importance of the pre-selected resilience challenges. The meaning of this was to evaluate whether some respondents would for example give a higher importance for “change in societal demand” referring to technosphere and market

resilience (increasing raw material demand for the needs of bioeconomy) instead of forest ecosystem resilience. In addition, we highlighted in the case of Finland that although we acknowledge the importance of resilience challenges vary across the country, in the exercise the experts should consider the whole country.

To establish the framework of participatory decision-making, pairwise comparisons are at the center of our analysis to assess resilience challenges and measures within the context of forest ecosystems and associated value chains. In this setting we are focusing on three different expert groups: i) forest-based industry representatives ii) experts such as forest researchers or NGOs, and iii) forest owners.

The experts were tasked with pairwise comparisons, evaluating the relative importance and effectiveness of each challenge and measure within their specific regional context, by using their knowledge, skill and intuition.

3.2 Data gathering

In pairwise comparisons, experts assess the relative importance of two elements on a ratio scale that ranges from equality in importance (represented by a numerical value of one) to complete preference for one element over the other (indicated by a numerical value of nine) (Table 1). The question for each pairwise comparison is how much more important an element is than others.

Table 1 Scale of relative importance (Saaty, 2005)

1	Equally important
3	Slightly more/less important
5	Strongly more/less important
7	Very strongly more/less important
9	Extremely more/less important
	Intermediate values for intermediate
2,4,6,8	judgements

Figure 1 outlines the four resilience challenges and the eight resilience measures that the experts were asked to evaluate, which resulted in a total of six pairwise comparisons for the resilience challenges and 28 pairwise comparisons for the resilience measures that each participant had to answer. Challenges and measures have been compared separately from one another, because resilience measures within forest ecosystems and wood value chains could not be straightforwardly linked to specific challenges due to their tendency to address multiple challenges simultaneously, without distinct associations to singular a challenge.

Figure 1 Pairwise comparison framework

In this pilot study we received 30 responses from Finnish experts. To allow for expert groups specific analysis of the pairwise comparison data we asked participants to specify their background, specifically if they work in forest or wood industry, if they are forest owners and if they work in forest-related research. Results of the expert’s background is presented in Table 2. The experts were allowed to be in multiple groups at the same time (i.e. forest researcher AND forest owner), thus the number does not sum up 30. For a more detailed overview of participants' backgrounds, see the expert matrix in the appendix 8.2.1. The questionnaire and the assessments collected from participants are attached as supplementary materials to this report in section 7.1 and 7.2 respectively.

Table 2 Respondent’s background

Respondent’s background	Number of respondents
<i>Forest-based industry</i>	7
<i>Forest owner</i>	14
<i>Forest researcher</i>	20

3.3 Data analysis

Pairwise comparison data collected from experts, (i.e., assessments on resilience challenges and measures) have been aggregated into pairwise comparison matrices that served as the input data into R. We conducted an in-depth analysis using the “ahpsurvey” package in R to

derive priority weights for various identified challenges and measures. The full code is attached to this deliverable as supplementary material (see section 7.3).

Individual preference weights were computed using eigenvalue method to capture experts' judgments. Additionally, the aggregation of individual preference weights have been derived through by normalising individual matrices to ensure that the aggregated assessments add up to one. Visualisation techniques, including bar plots and box plots, were employed to illustrate the prioritisation of resilience measures and highlight any discrepancies among experts' judgments.

3.4 Case-study description: Finland

Forests cover 70% of Finland's land area. The main commercial species are Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and birch (*Betula* spp.). Growing stock is 2529 Mm³, annual harvest around 76 Mm³, and annual growth has been reported to be approximately 103 Mm³ (Vaahtera et al. 2023). Protected forest land in Finland is around 2.9 Mha which is around 13% of the total forest area (Vaahtera et al. 2023). Forest ownership in Finland is predominantly private (52%) (Vaahtera et al. 2023). The state owns 35% of Finnish forest land, companies own 8% and the rest 6% are owned by other institutions like municipalities or parishes (Vaahtera et al. 2023). Of the industrial roundwood removals around 37% was pulpwood and 29% sawlogs in 2021, showing that the pulp industry is the dominant forest-based industry in Finland (Vaahtera et al. 2023). Forest damages, lowering the quality of forests used for wood production, occurred in 4.1 Mha in 2022, which was around 1 Mha less than in 2021 (Terhonen et al. 2023). However, the harvest operations made due to bark beetle risk (*Ips Typographus*) were increased compared to previous years, although the total damages (evaluated in damaged area) decreased (Terhonen et al. 2023). Abiotic damages (including e.g. wind, snow and flood) covered around 45% of the damages and the rest were damages caused by insects, mooses, diseases and other biotic factors (Terhonen et al. 2023). Changing climate increases the risk for both, abiotic and biotic forest disturbances in the future. There has also been concerns related to raw material sufficiency to the contrast of increasing demand to substitute non-wood industrial products and goals to increase the area for forest conservation.

Figure 2 Case study region - Finland

4. Results

4.1 Resilience challenges

When looking at all the experts' responses together, biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems emerged as the most significant concern, with a prioritised weight of 0.364, followed by tree species suitability (to adapt climate change) at 0.289, increased risk of forest disturbances at 0.193, and change in societal demand (increasing raw material demand for the needs of bioeconomy) at 0.154 (Figure 3).

There were small differences among different expert groups in the resilience challenge rankings as well as in the given priority weights. The resulting priority ranks obtained from forest-based industry representatives are as follows: The most prioritized was tree species suitability (0.345), followed by biodiversity decline (0.251), increased risk of forest disturbances (0.245), and lastly change in societal demands (0.159) (Figure 3). Forest researchers/NGOs however, prioritized the most biodiversity decline with highest priority weight given in any group (0.411). The second prioritized challenge was tree species suitability (0.261), third increased risk of forest disturbances (0.178), and the last change in societal demands (0.150) (Figure 3). The responses from forest owners were a mixture of responses consisting of 6 forest researchers, 4 forest-based industry representatives, and 4 forest owners without research/industrial background. Therefore, the responses were the closest to the responses gained from the researchers/NGOs. The priority weights of resilience challenges according to Finnish forest owners are as follows: Biodiversity decline as priority one (0.329), followed by

tree species suitability (0.284), increased risk of forest disturbances (0.211) and lastly change in societal demands (0.177).

The highest priority weight for the biodiversity decline was obtained from the forest researchers/NGOs (over 0.4), whereas the priority weight given within the expert group of forest-based industries was noticeably lower (0.25). Considering tree species suitability, the forest-based industry gave the highest weight whereas forest researchers/NGO’s weight was noticeably lower (0.345 vs 0.178). Regarding other challenges, the differences between expert groups were smaller.

Figure 3 Priority weights of resilience challenges including responses of all participants (N=30), forest-based industry (N=7), Forest owners (N=14) and forest researchers/NGO’s (N=20)

4.2 Resilience measures

The results including all the expert responses from the pairwise comparison approach determined the aggregated priority weights for resilience measures within Finland's forests and forest-based value chains. The resulting values obtained are: 1. Increasing the share of forest area under protection (0.205), 2. Increasing the share of mixed species forests (0.195), 3. increasing people employed within forest value chain (0.141), 4. tightening criteria for forest certificates (0.127), 5. increasing the share of uneven-aged forests (0.119), 6. Increase in felling volume (0.086), 7. increasing forest network density (0.071), and 8. increasing the share of forests where clear-cutting is performed (0.057) (Figure 4).

Increasing the share of forest area under protection emerges as the most significant measure, aligning well with the importance attributed to addressing the resilience challenge of

biodiversity decline. Increasing the share of forests where clear-cutting is performed emerges as the least prioritised measure. This suggests a lower level of importance attributed to this strategy compared to others. Clear-cutting is often associated with ecological disruption, habitat loss, and reduced biodiversity. Therefore, experts may perceive it as a less desirable approach for enhancing the resilience of Finland's forests and forest-based value chains.

Comparing the opinions of different expert groups, the weights and rankings were similar within the groups of forest owners and forest researchers/NGO's. The most prioritized measure in both groups was "increasing the share of forest area under protection" and the second prioritized was "Increasing the share of mixed species forests". The least prioritized measures in both groups were increasing the share of forests where clearcutting is performed, increasing forest network density, and increase in felling volume. This is most likely caused by the fact that 6 of the respondents in the forest owner group were researchers, thus their opinions may dominate the results. Only relatively differences in the weightings occurred regarding rest of the measures (figure 4). The biggest difference (difference between weightings 0.03) was regarding uneven aged forests. Forest owners were a little more hesitant to prioritize the share of uneven aged forests than the researchers in general.

The expert group of forest researchers/NGOs gave the highest importance for increasing the share of forest area under protection (0.218) and the lowest for increasing the share of forests where clearcutting is performed (0.048) (Figure 4). The importance for the rest of measures were given in the following ranking order: 2. increasing the share of mixed species forests (0.191), 3. increasing people employed within the forest value chain (0.140), 4. tightening criteria for forest certificates (0.137), 5. increasing the share of uneven-aged forests (0.129), 6. increase felling volume (0.076), and 7. increasing forest road network density (0.062) (Figure 4). The results are very similar to the overall results, due to the large share of this expert group of the overall participants.

The most difference in ranking orders as well as priority weights compared to other expert groups occurred in the forest-based industries expert group. The aggregated prioritisation results from forest-based industry experts reflect the priorities of this expert group: 1. Increasing the share of mixed species forests (0.201), 2. increasing people employed within the forest value chain (0.149), 3. increasing the share of forest area under protection (0.134), 4. increasing the share of uneven-aged forests (0.122), 5. Increase felling volume (0.111), 6. increasing forest road network density (0.110), 7. tightening criteria for forest certificates (0.103), and 8. increasing the share of forests where clear-cutting is performed (0.070) (Figure 4). The biggest difference in weighting within this group occurred in 'increasing the share of forest area under protection' (the weight difference to other groups around 0.9), meaning that

although the forest-based industry experts consider forest protection highly important in general, they are hesitant to state it would be much more important than other measures presented in this survey. According to these results, forest-based industry representatives highlighted increasing the share of mixed species forests and boosting employment within the forest value chain as top priorities. Increasing the share of forests subject to clear-cutting emerged as the least favoured measure among forest-based industry representatives, although clear-cutting is a widespread form of harvesting forests.

Figure 4 Priority weights of resilience challenges including responses of all participants (N=30), forest-based industry (N=7), Forest owners (N=14) and forest researchers/NGO's (N=20)

5. Discussion

This deliverable (D.5.3) carried out a preliminary assessment of key resilience measures including their given priorities along forest systems and forest value chains. The resilience

here is defined as resilience of the whole forest-value chain in the region in question, although the resilience measures in the analysis largely focus on the forest ecosystem resilience in contrast to e.g. market resilience. The analysis was implemented as an expert panel assessment, applying a multi-criteria method and providing information of the prioritized resilience challenges and preferred measures to response these challenges among different expert groups. In this context, it was not possible to establish a clear decision hierarchy in the analysis of expert preferences on resilience challenges and measures in forest ecosystems and wood value chains using a pairwise comparison approach. This was primarily due to the interconnectedness of resilience measures, which often address multiple challenges simultaneously rather than being distinctly linked to a single challenge. The results of this deliverable focus on the first case study, Finland.

The prioritised measures among forest-based industry representatives attend the emphasised future threats. Increasing the share of mixed species forests lowers the risks related to e.g. insect and fungal damages, thus providing an important tool to improve resilience in boreal forests. Climate change imposes the risk of bark beetle damages and root rot in coniferous forests (Venäläinen et al. 2020), thus this risk can be lowered by introducing more non-coniferous species in Finnish forests. Also, mixed species forests can improve biodiversity in boreal forests (Dubois et al. 2023), thus responding to the resilience challenge regarding biodiversity loss. Increasing mixed species forest areas was recognised as one of the synergies between resilience challenges “biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems” and “change in societal demand (increasing raw material demand for the needs of bioeconomy)” in RESONATE D1.3. However, the introduction of more non-coniferous tree species poses challenges for forest-based industries in Finland, particularly since most of the production relies on softwood. This shift may necessitate resilience measures within the industries, as it could potentially affect the availability and suitability of raw materials for sawmilling and pulp production. Notably, non-coniferous fibers tend to be shorter, making them more suitable for bleaching and thus primarily used for printing paper.

Printing paper production is anticipated to decrease in the future while demand for packaging and textile fibers is increasing, which may hinder the uses of softwood. However, non-coniferous fibers could be used for these purposes as well, if nanotechnology (nano fibers) are applied. Also sawmilling industry prefers coniferous trees since they have lower density making them more applicable for processing. Non-coniferous trees are not currently used either for engineered wood products such as CLT (Cross-laminated timber) or LVL (Laminated veneer lumber), but in the future it might be possible due to technology changes (Lauri et al. 2021). The interlinkage between increasing the product portfolio through innovations and measures improving forest stand resilience was also pointed out in the study of Hoeben et al.

2023. For example, cellulosic nanomaterials made from non-coniferous wood could offer applications as fillers and coatings to improve quality of packaging and paper products. The forest-based industry representatives may have considered that these required innovation measures in the technosystem when ranking mixed species forests as the priority one. They ranked 'increasing the number of people employed within forest value chain' the second highest, indicating that they might recognise the need to expand expertise regarding new products and services in the forest value chain. Increasing the share of uneven aged forests, ranked the fourth in importance among forest-based industry representatives, benefits the sawmilling industry by yielding more sawlogs over time through the harvesting from the above-method. Yet, the pulpmilling industry dominates the wood uses in Finland by using 32,6 million m³, whereas sawlogs harvested for the needs of the wood product industries was only 26,3 million m³ in 2023 (Natural Resources Institute Finland, 2024). Thus, decreasing the share of pulplogs could impose a risk for raw material sufficiency.

The expert group of forest researchers/NGOs gave the highest importance for decline of biodiversity, and the second highest importance for change in tree species suitability. The least importance was given for change in societal demand (increasing raw material demand for the needs of bioeconomy), similarly as within the expert group consisting of forest-based industry representatives. In line with the ranked resilience challenges, they gave the highest importance for increasing the share of forest area (rank 1) under protection and increasing the share of mixed species forests (rank 2). The result was anticipated, since biodiversity is recognised one of the corner stones in ecological sustainability that affects many other resilience areas (Hekkala et al. 2023). Nevertheless, the challenges of "biodiversity decline in forest ecosystems" and "tree species suitability to adapt climate change" are closely linked. Resilience measures aimed to addressing these challenges often serve to tackle both issues simultaneously. However, increasing area of protected forests may hinder recreational activities as a trade-off, as recognised in D5.3. This trade-off can be minimised by ensuring enough recreational zones in protected areas.

Similarly, as within the expert group of forest-based industry representatives, increasing the employment within forest value chain was ranked third in terms of importance. Increasing the share of forests where clearcutting is performed was considered the least important, similarly as among industrial experts. The industrial experts and researchers in general had similar opinions of the most and least important resilience measures. However, some differences appeared; for instance, researchers considered tightening of forest certificates more important than the forest-based industry representatives.

Forest owners consisted of six forest researchers, and four forest-based industry representatives, and four experts with no industry/research background. The ranking of resilience measures aligned with the priorities identified by the forest researchers/NGOs and forest-based industry representatives, with mixed species forests, forest area protection, and employment initiatives receiving the highest importance. The measure of increasing road network density did not receive high importance rates among any expert group, since it was generally commented that the forest road network is already quite well performing in Finland.

The study was conducted as an expert panel analysis and therefore does not, nor aim, to represent Finland's citizens. However, the opinions of the selected professionals reflect well most critical resilience challenges and their related measures highlighted in the recent literature and media. The presentation of the results from Finland marks the beginning of the application of the integrated assessment in Task 5.2 in other case study regions (Galicia Spain, Germany), setting the stage for data-driven decision-making in the upcoming stages of the project. The comparison is done by considering country-specific circumstances such as forest structure, main concerns, and industrial structure. This helps to better understand possible bottle necks in resilience policy making and enables tailored recommendations.

It should be noted that although the analysis focused on overall resilience of the whole forest value chain, the background of the expert likely affects the prioritisation of resilience measures regarding "resilience *to what*". For example, forest ecology researchers may emphasize more resilience of forest ecosystem, whereas forest-based industry representatives likely consider resilience of markets and raw material supply as well. Therefore, we recruited experts from all parts of the forest value chain to the expert panel. However, we did consider resilience measures related to technosystem innovations nor product portfolio changes, thus it is unclear which measures specifically should be prioritised on that side in their opinion. The reason for excluding those measures was that 1) industrial structures vary between case study countries, thus it renders utilisation of equally applicable measures 2) the RESONATE case studies did not consider such measures either, which were utilised as a basis for this study and 3) technological innovations and service sector are generally difficult to quantify. This should be the next core focus in future studies to better understand the whole scope of forest resilience and e.g. more optimally allocate R&D funding. More detailed analysis considering different elements of the forest value chain resilience and interlinkages between them could be carried out by using Operational Resilience Framework (ORF) presented in the RESONATE D1.4 (Lloret et al. 2023).

6. Conclusions

The responses of the forest-based industry representatives, forest researchers and forest owners emphasise the importance of forest biodiversity decline and tree species suitability to adapt climate change among four different resilience challenges, when considering the whole forest-value chain. Their prioritised resilience measures support this priority order of resilience challenges, highlighting the importance to increase increasing the share of protected forest areas and mixed species forest, and tightening the forest certification standards, as well as increasing the share of uneven aged forests. Yet, it is implied the respondents recognise the need to adopt innovations and increase the diversity of services- and products in the technosystem, since they gave the highest importance rates for employment in the forest value chain right after forest protection and mixed species forests. This would respond the challenge of changing societal demand for wood. It was also commented among the experts, that these resilience challenges are not separate from each other.

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8. Supplementary materials

8.1 Questionnaire

Forest ecosystem and forest value-chain resilience assessment/survey/questionnaire

Participant's name:

Participant's email:

Institution:

Welcome to the RESONATE survey aimed at shaping the resilient future of Finland's forest ecosystems and wood-value chain. Resilience, the cornerstone of thriving ecosystems and industries when facing future uncertainties, can be measured in many different areas. In RESONATE, our primary focus is on addressing pivotal resilience challenges prevalent in the forest value chains.

While recognising the regional diversity within Finland, our survey centers on the entire nation as a holistic entity. Though certain challenges might exhibit varying relevance across regions, we urge you to deliberate on the overall context of Finland when expressing your insights.

In the initial phase of this survey, we invite you to engage in a vital exercise of pairwise comparison. Your unique perspective will help us assess the relative significance of the identified resilience challenges. By systematically ranking these challenges against each other, drawing from your personal opinions, you contribute to a more nuanced understanding of their importance towards integrated resilience of forest ecosystems and the wood-value chain in Finland.

Moving forward, the second segment of the survey extends the principle of pairwise comparison. Here, we kindly request you to evaluate different resilience measures within the context of Finland's forest value chains.

Your participation in this survey plays an important role in co-creating resilience blueprints for Finland's forests and wood-value chain. Your opinions, forming the basis for multi-criteria analysis, will help policymakers, industry representatives and researchers to guide decisions that safeguard the sustainability and vitality of forests as invaluable ecosystems and economic drivers.

Thank you for dedicating your time and insights to the RESONATE initiative. Together, we pave the way for a more resilient and thriving future for Finland's forests and the entire wood-value chain.

Figure 1 Pairwise comparisons between resilience challenges

How important are the following resilience challenges in your opinion, when compared against each other, considering the overall resilience of forest value-chains?
 For each pair of challenges, please rank each pair of challenges based on their relative importance, using the 9-point scale.
 Choose the value that best reflects the challenge you believe should hold greater/lesser significance in enhancing the resilience of forest ecosystems and the wood-value chain in Finland.

9-Point Scale:
 1 - Equal Importance
 3 - Slightly more/less important
 5 - Strongly more/less important
 7 - Very strongly more/less important
 9 - Extremely more/less important
 2, 4, 6, 8 - Intermediate values for intermediate judgments

	More important than							Equal	less important than									
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Biodiveristy decline in forest ecosystems																		Change in societal demand (changing raw material demand for the society)
Biodiveristy decline in forest ecosystems																		Tree species suitability to adapt climate change
Biodiveristy decline in forest ecosystems																		Increased risk of disturbances (forest fires, wind/snow damages, insect/fungal damages)
Change in societal demand (changing raw material demand for the society)																		Tree species suitability to adapt climate change
Change in societal demand (changing raw material demand for the society)																		Increased risk of disturbances (forest fires, wind/snow damages, insect/fungal damages)
Tree species suitability to adapt climate change																		Increased risk of disturbances (forest fires, wind/snow damages, insect/fungal damages)

Figure 2 Pairwise comparisons between resilience measures

How important are the following resilience actions in your opinion, when compared against each other, in terms of prioritizing the resilience of forest value-chains in Finland?

Please rank each pair of actions based on their relative priority using the 9-point scale.

Choose the value that best reflects the action you believe should hold greater/lesser significance in enhancing the resilience of forest ecosystems and the wood-value chain in Finland.

9-Point Scale:
 1 - Equal importance
 3 - Slightly more/less important
 5 - Strongly more/less important
 7 - Very strongly more/less important
 9 - Extremely more/less important
 2, 4, 6, 8 - Intermediate values for intermediate judgments

	More important than	Equal	less important than	
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of uneven-aged forests
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area under protection
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing people employed in forest operations
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of certified forest area
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increase in felling volume (increase timber supplied for the industries)	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area under protection
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing people employed in forest operations
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of certified forest area
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of uneven-aged forests	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area under protection
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing people employed in forest operations
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of certified forest area
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of forest area where clearcutting is used	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing people employed in forest operations
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of certified forest area
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of forest area under protection	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing people employed in forest operations	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of certified forest area
Increasing people employed in forest operations	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increasing people employed in forest operations	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing people employed in forest operations	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing people employed in forest operations	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of certified forest area	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed
Increasing share of certified forest area	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing share of certified forest area	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed
Increasing share of forest area where selection cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density
Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing share of mixed-species forests
Increasing share of forest area where shelterwood cutting is performed	9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	Increasing road network density

8.2 Raw data of all respondents

8.2.1 Full expert matrix

Respondent	Forest-based industry	Forest owner	Forest (ecology/other) researcher
r1		X	X
r2			X
r3		X	
r4		X	
r5			X

r6	x	x	
r7	x		x
r8		x	
r9			x
r10	x	x	
r11		x	x
r12	x		
r13			x
r14		x	
r15			x
r16			x
r17	x		
r18	x	x	
r19		x	x
r20			x
r21			x
r22			x
r23		x	x
r24			x
r25			x
r26		x	x
r27			x
r28			x
r29		x	x
r30	x	x	

8.2.2 Raw data of pairwise comparisons between resilience challenges

Respondent	bio_soc	bio_spe	bio_dis	soc_spe	soc_dis	spe_dis
1	1	1	2	-2	1	1
2	9	8	7	-2	-2	1
3	-7	-8	-7	3	3	-3
4	8	8	8	-8	1	6
5	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	7	1	1	-4	-3	3
7	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	6	6	1	-5	-5	6
9	8	6	5	2	2	-2
10	1	-6	1	1	-5	1
11	-9	-2	-2	3	1	1
12	7	-7	1	-3	-7	6
13	7	7	2	-6	-3	3
14	-2	-4	-2	-4	-2	3
15	1	2	2	2	-2	-2

16	6	5	5	-4	1	1
17	2	-3	4	-2	4	2
18	4	2	3	-4	-6	-5
19	4	2	3	-2	1	-2
20	3	1	1	1	1	1
21	1	2	9	3	1	1
22	8	1	8	-8	-8	1
23	8	8	8	-6	2	6
24	6	2	9	-9	-8	3
25	7	1	5	-8	-4	5
26	9	1	7	1	-7	7
27	5	-4	-7	-4	-6	5
28	5	-6	5	-5	-4	7
29	3	1	5	-2	3	1
30	-2	-2	-2	1	1	1

8.2.3 Raw data of pairwise comparisons between resilience measures

Respondent	vol_unev	vol_cc	vol_prot	vol_empl	vol_cert	vol_mix	vol_road	unev_cc	unev_prot
1	3	2	-2	9	1	-2	2	-2	-2
2	-9	1	-9	1	-4	-9	1	9	-3
3	5	2	5	-5	6	4	4	-5	-3
4	-9	1	-9	-4	-5	-7	1	6	-6
5	7	7	8	1	3	1	4	4	1
6	1	1	-2	-9	-6	-9	1	9	-7
7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	1	1	-9	1	-9	-9	1	4	-9
9	-7	1	-7	2	-2	-4	1	8	2
10	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
11	-4	-6	8	-7	-6	-4	-5	7	8
12	1	4	4	1	5	1	-4	-5	5
13	-8	-3	-9	-9	-5	-8	1	9	-6
14	5	1	2	6	2	-4	1	-4	-2
15	-2	2	1	1	-2	-2	2	2	2
16	-4	1	-4	-2	1	-4	1	6	1
17	-5	2	-4	-8	-2	-8	1	8	5
18	-4	1	-4	5	-4	-4	4	7	1
19	-6	2	-5	-2	-2	-6	1	8	-3
20	1	7	-5	-7	-3	-6	1	4	-6
21	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
22	8	2	-2	-9	-8	-9	8	-7	-9
23	-5	4	-9	-6	-8	-8	1	4	-7
24	-7	1	-5	-9	-3	-5	1	7	3
25	-5	9	-9	-5	-9	1	7	9	-7
26	1	1	-9	1	-7	-9	1	1	-3
27	-3	7	-2	-4	-3	-4	-2	3	-2

28	-3	1	-3	-4	-2	-4	-4	4	-3
29	-5	1	-5	-3	-5	-9	3	7	-3
30	4	4	4	1	4	2	-2	-2	2

Respondent	unev_empl	unev_cert	unev_mix	unev_road	cc_prot	cc_empl	cc_cert	cc_mix	cc_road
1	-3	-2	-3	1	-2	-2	1	-2	1
2	5	4	1	9	-9	-9	-9	-9	1
3	-6	-3	-7	-3	4	-3	4	3	1
4	3	1	3	7	-9	-8	-7	-8	1
5	-3	5	-4	3	-2	-2	1	-2	1
6	6	2	-4	9	-9	-3	-9	-9	1
7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	1	-9	-9	1	-9	1	-9	-9	1
9	4	2	3	8	-9	-8	-8	-9	-3
10	-5	5	1	1	1	1	2	1	1
11	-7	-4	-7	-6	-6	-7	-5	-6	-7
12	4	5	-5	-7	1	-4	4	-6	4
13	7	7	1	9	-9	-6	-7	-6	1
14	1	-3	-8	-3	4	4	3	-2	4
15	2	2	-2	2	-2	1	-2	-2	1
16	2	-5	1	6	-8	-6	-8	-7	1
17	-4	4	-2	1	-2	-6	1	-5	-2
18	-5	1	1	5	-5	1	-5	-5	1
19	4	3	-4	5	-6	-2	-4	-7	-2
20	-5	1	-7	1	-6	-6	-3	-7	-4
21	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
22	-9	-8	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9
23	-5	-5	-5	6	-8	-7	-6	-6	1
24	1	5	-5	5	-3	-7	1	-5	1
25	5	-7	5	3	-9	-7	-9	-9	-7
26	3	1	1	7	-5	7	-6	-4	1
27	-4	-3	-5	-2	-2	-4	-2	1	-2
28	-4	3	-4	4	-3	-4	-2	-3	-4
29	-3	1	-5	5	-9	-5	-7	-9	1
30	-6	2	-6	-4	3	-2	1	-3	-2

Respondent	prot_empl	prot_cert	prot_mix	prot_road	empl_cert	empl_mix	empl_road
1	-2	-2	-2	2	1	1	2
2	9	9	9	9	1	-2	1
3	-4	-3	-4	1	6	5	5
4	6	7	7	9	1	-4	7
5	-4	4	-4	2	5	1	5
6	9	8	8	9	-8	-8	5
7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	9	9	5	9	1	1	1

9	8	8	8	8	-2	-6	1
10	1	1	-5	-4	3	1	1
11	-7	-6	1	1	1	1	1
12	-8	-7	-6	4	7	-5	-7
13	7	8	6	9	-4	-5	6
14	2	-4	-7	1	-3	-7	-3
15	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
16	-4	2	5	9	-4	-2	9
17	-6	1	-5	1	5	-2	7
18	5	1	2	5	-4	-4	1
19	5	3	2	6	-2	-5	2
20	1	3	-5	3	5	-4	5
21	-2	1	1	2	1	1	1
22	2	-2	1	9	-2	-2	9
23	8	7	7	9	-3	3	5
24	1	5	-5	1	3	1	5
25	9	1	7	9	-9	-7	-5
26	5	1	1	5	1	-3	1
27	-2	1	-3	2	2	3	3
28	3	3	3	3	4	3	4
29	4	3	1	7	3	-5	5
30	-4	-2	-6	-4	4	-2	-2

Respondent	cert_mix	cert_road	mix_road
1	-2	1	4
2	-5	3	9
3	-5	1	1
4	8	9	9
5	-5	-2	5
6	3	8	8
7	1	1	1
8	1	1	1
9	-6	4	8
10	-9	-9	1
11	1	1	1
12	-7	4	6
13	7	9	9
14	-4	1	4
15	2	2	2
16	5	9	8
17	-4	1	4
18	3	6	5
19	-3	5	7
20	-5	3	6
21	1	1	1

22	1	9	9
23	4	8	8
24	-7	1	5
25	9	9	7
26	1	4	4
27	-2	-2	-2
28	-2	-2	3
29	-7	5	8
30	-4	-4	3

8.3 R-Code for data analysis

8.3.1 R-code for analysis of resilience challenges

Load the ahpsurvey package

```
install.packages("ahpsurvey")
```

```
install.packages("dplyr") #!Loop
```

```
install.packages("tidyverse")
```

```
install.packages("ggplot2") #! Loop
```

```
install.packages("kableExtra")
```

```
library(ahpsurvey)
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
library(kableExtra)
```

Load your data from CSV file. choose CSV data according to analysis focus (e.g. different expert groups)

#Choose file according to expert group!

```
Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_aggregated_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
```

Choose file according to expert group!

```
#Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_industry_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";") #Industry experts only
```



```
#Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_owner_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";") #Forest
owners only

#Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_researcher_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Researchers only

#Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_owner_industry_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Forest owners, that are also industry experts

#Q1_data <- read.csv("Test_Q1_owner_research_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Forest owners, that are also researchers

warning("Please check whether the correct CSV has been read from the working directory")

# Define criteria or attributes

atts <- c("biodiversity", "social_demand", "species_suitability", "disturbances")

#creating pairwise comparison matrices

Q1_data_ahp <- Q1_data %>%

  ahp.mat(atts = atts, negconvert = FALSE)

#Individual preference weights using eigenvalues

Q1_ind <- ahp.indpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts, method = "eigen")

Q1_ind

# find individual responses with high inconsistencies

eigentrue <- ahp.indpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts, method = "eigen")

geom <- ahp.indpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts, method = "arithmetic")

error <- data.frame(id = 1:length(Q1_data_ahp), maxdiff = apply(abs(eigentrue - geom), 1,
max))

error %>%

  ggplot(aes(x = id, y = maxdiff)) +

  geom_point() +

  geom_hline(yintercept = 0.05, linetype = "dashed", color = "red") +

  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "gray50") +
```



```

scale_x_continuous("Respondent ID") +
scale_y_continuous("Maximum difference") +
theme_minimal()

#### Aggregated individual judgements

Q1_ind_agg <- Q1_data %>%
ahp.mat(atts = atts, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
ahp.aggjudge(atts, aggmethod = "geometric")

Q1_ind_agg

#### Aggregated preference weights

Q1_agg_arit <- ahp.aggpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts = atts, method = "arithmetic")
Q1_agg_geom <- ahp.aggpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts = atts, method = "geometric")
Q1_agg_eigen <- ahp.aggpref(Q1_data_ahp, atts = atts, method = "eigen")

Q1_agg_arit # always 1. Sensitive to extreme values
Q1_agg_geom # Less sensitive to extreme values
Q1_agg_eigen # Complex. Analysis of the consistency through the calculation of
eigenvalues and eigenvector

#### Consistency check that shows how many and which respondents are above the 10%
consistency threshold

CR <- Q1_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
  ahp.cr(atts)

table(CR <= 0.1)

above_threshold <- CR > 0.1

individuals_above_threshold <- Q1_data[above_threshold, ]

print(individuals_above_threshold)

### Show mean aggregated CR for all respondents

```



```

mean_aggregated_CR <- mean(CR)

mean_aggregated_CR

### For consistency check - Show pairwise comparisons that are most prone to
inconsistencies

Q1_data_ahp %>%

  ahp.pwerror(atts) %>%

  gather(top1, top2, top3, key = "max", value = "pair") %>%

  table() %>%

  as.data.frame() %>%

  ggplot(aes(x = pair, y = Freq, fill = max)) +

  geom_bar(stat = 'identity') +

  scale_y_continuous("Frequency", breaks = c(seq(0,180,20))) +

  scale_fill_discrete(breaks = c("top1", "top2", "top3"), labels = c("1", "2", "3")) +

  scale_x_discrete("Pair") +

  guides(fill = guide_legend(title="Rank")) +

  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 20, hjust = 1),

        panel.background = element_rect(fill = NA),

        panel.grid.major.y = element_line(colour = "grey80"),

        panel.grid.major.x = element_blank(),

        panel.ontop = FALSE)

## Show inconsistencies of individual pairwise comparisons in matrix format. Higher values
indicate higher inconsistencies

#In essence this shows the same thing as the boxplot with inconsistencies coded
above

gm_mean <- function(x, na.rm=TRUE){

  exp(sum(log(x[x > 0])), na.rm=na.rm) / length(x))

}

```



```
incon_mat <- Q1_data_ahp %>%
  ahp.error(atts, reciprocal = TRUE) %>%
  unlist() %>%
  as.numeric() %>%
  array(dim=c(length(atts), length(atts), length(Q1_data_ahp))) %>%
  apply(c(1,2), gm_mean)
colnames(incon_mat) <- rownames(incon_mat) <- atts
incon_mat

### Dealing with inconsistencies ahp.harker
consistent <- Q1_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts = atts, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
  ahp.harker(atts, iterations = 5, stopcr = 0.1, limit = T, round = T, printiter = F) %>%
  ahp.aggpref(atts, method = "eigen")
consistent

#### Plotting results
#Table of priority weights
# Install and load necessary packages
#install.packages("kableExtra")
#install.packages("dplyr")
#library(kableExtra)
#library(dplyr)
# Create a data frame. PLEASE ADJUST arit; geom; or eigen!!
result_df <- data.frame(
  Resilience_challenges = c("Biodiversity decline", "Change in societal demands", "Tree
species suitability", "Risk of disturbances"),
  Priorities = round(Q1_agg_arit, 3),
```



```
Rank = rank(-Q1_agg_arit, ties.method = "min")
)
# Print the table with kableExtra styling
result_table <- result_df %>%
  kable("html") %>%
  kable_styling(full_width = FALSE)
# Print the styled table without the original names column
print(result_table)
#### Plot Results in box plot
Resilience_challenges = c("Biodiversity decline", "Change in societal demands", "Tree
species suitability", "Risk of disturbances")
#The following function use also Q1_agg_arit/geom/eigen and mean_aggregated_CR
# Create a data frame
plot_data <- data.frame(
  Resilience_challenges = Resilience_challenges,
  Aggregated_Priorities = Q1_agg_arit
)
# Plot
#install.packages("ggplot2")
#library(ggplot2)
ggplot(plot_data, aes(x = Aggregated_Priorities, y = Resilience_challenges)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", fill = "skyblue") +
  labs(title = "Priority Weights of Resilience Challenges", x = "Aggregated Priorities", y =
NULL) +
  #####change Title according to expert groups
  theme_minimal()
```


8.3.2 R-code for analysis of resilience measures

```
# Load the ahpsurvey package
install.packages("ahpsurvey")
install.packages("dplyr") #!Loop
install.packages("tidyverse")
install.packages("ggplot2") #!Loop
install.packages("kableExtra")

library(ahpsurvey)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyverse)
library(ggplot2)
library(kableExtra)

# Load your data from CSV file. choose CSV data according to analysis focus (e.g. different
expert groups)

#Choose file according to expert group!
#Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_aggregated_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
### Choose file according to expert group!
#Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_industry_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";") #Industry
experts only
#Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_owner_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";") #Forest
owners only
#Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_researcher_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Researchers only

Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_owner_industry_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Forest owners, that are also industry experts

#Q2_data <- read.csv("Test_Q2_owner_research_finland.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ";")
#Forest owners, that are also researchers

warning("Please check whether the correct CSV has been read from the working directory")

# Define criteria or attributes
atts_Q2 <- c("Increase in felling volume", "Increasing share of uneven-aged forests",
"Increasing share of forests where clearcutting is performed",

"Increasing share of forest area under protection", "Increasing people employed within the
forest value-chain", "Tightening criteria for forest certificates",

"Increasing the share of mixed-species forests", "Increasing forest road network density")

#creating pairwise comparison matrices
```



```

Q2_data_ahp <- Q2_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts = atts_Q2, negconvert = FALSE)
#Individual preference weights using eigenvalues
Q2_ind <- ahp.indpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts_Q2, method = "eigen")
Q2_ind
# find individual responses with high inconsistencies
eigentrue <- ahp.indpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts_Q2, method = "eigen")
geom <- ahp.indpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts_Q2, method = "arithmetic")
error <- data.frame(id = 1:length(Q2_data_ahp), maxdiff = apply(abs(eigentrue - geom), 1,
max))
error %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = id, y = maxdiff)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0.05, linetype = "dashed", color = "red") +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "gray50") +
  scale_x_continuous("Respondent ID") +
  scale_y_continuous("Maximum difference") +
  theme_minimal()
##### Aggregated individual judgements
Q2_ind_agg <- Q2_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts = atts_Q2, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
  ahp.aggjudge(atts_Q2, aggmethod = "geometric") #possible agg.method = arithmetic,
tgmean = trimmed geometric mean
Q2_ind_agg
##### Aggregated preference weights
Q2_agg_arit <- ahp.aggpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts = atts_Q2, method = "arithmetic")
Q2_agg_geom <- ahp.aggpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts = atts_Q2, method = "geometric")
Q2_agg_eigen <- ahp.aggpref(Q2_data_ahp, atts = atts_Q2, method = "eigen")
Q2_agg_arit # always 1. Sensitive to extreme values o
Q2_agg_geom # Less sensitive to extreme values
Q2_agg_eigen # Complex. Analysis of the consistency through the calculation of
eigenvalues and eigenvector
##### Consistency check that shows how many and which respondents are above the 10%
consistency threshold

```



```

CR_Q2 <- Q2_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts_Q2, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
  ahp.cr(atts_Q2)
table(CR_Q2 <= 0.1)
above_threshold_Q2 <- CR_Q2 > 0.1
individuals_above_threshold_Q2 <- Q2_data[above_threshold_Q2, ]
print(individuals_above_threshold_Q2)
### Show mean aggregated CR for all respondents
mean_aggregated_CR_Q2 <- mean(CR_Q2)
mean_aggregated_CR_Q2
### For consistency check - Show pairwise comparisons that are most prone to
inconsistencies
Q2_data_ahp %>%
  ahp.pwerror(atts_Q2) %>%
  gather(top1, top2, top3, key = "max", value = "pair") %>%
  table() %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = pair, y = Freq, fill = max)) +
  geom_bar(stat = 'identity') +
  scale_y_continuous("Frequency", breaks = c(seq(0,180,20))) +
  scale_fill_discrete(breaks = c("top1", "top2", "top3"), labels = c("1", "2", "3")) +
  scale_x_discrete("Pair") +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title="Rank")) +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 20, hjust = 1),
        panel.background = element_rect(fill = NA),
        panel.grid.major.y = element_line(colour = "grey80"),
        panel.grid.major.x = element_blank(),
        panel.ontop = FALSE)
## Show inconsistencies of individual pairwise comparisons in matrix format. Higher values
indicate higher inconsistencies
#In essence this shows the same thing as the boxplot with inconsistencies coded above
gm_mean_Q2 <- function(x, na.rm=TRUE){
  exp(sum(log(x[x > 0])), na.rm=na.rm) / length(x))

```



```

}
incon_mat_Q2 <- Q2_data_ahp %>%
  ahp.error(atts_Q2, reciprocal = TRUE) %>%
  unlist() %>%
  as.numeric() %>%
  array(dim=c(length(atts_Q2), length(atts_Q2), length(Q2_data_ahp))) %>%
  apply(c(1,2), gm_mean_Q2)
colnames(incon_mat_Q2) <- rownames(incon_mat_Q2) <- atts_Q2
incon_mat_Q2
### Dealing with inconsistencies ahp.harker
consistent_Q2 <- Q2_data %>%
  ahp.mat(atts = atts_Q2, negconvert = FALSE) %>%
  ahp.harker(atts_Q2, iterations = 5, stopcr = 0.1, limit = T, round = T, printiter = F) %>%
  ahp.aggpref(atts_Q2, method = "eigen")
consistent_Q2
#### Plotting results
#Table of priority weights
# Install and load necessary packages
#install.packages("kableExtra")
#install.packages("dplyr")
#library(kableExtra)
#library(dplyr)
# Create a data frame. PLEASE ADJUST arit; geom; or eigen!!
result_df_Q2 <- data.frame(
  Resilience_measures = c("Increase in felling volume", "Increasing share of uneven-aged
forests", "Increasing share of forests where clearcutting is performed",
  "Increasing share of forest area under protection", "Increasing people
employed within the forest value-chain", "Tightening criteria for forest certificates",
  "Increasing the share of mixed-species forests", "Increasing forest road
network density"),
  Priorities = round(Q2_agg_arit, 3),
  Rank = rank(-Q2_agg_arit, ties.method = "min")
)

```



```

# Print the table with kableExtra styling
result_table_Q2 <- result_df_Q2 %>%
  kable("html") %>%
  kable_styling(full_width = FALSE)
# Print the styled table without the original names column
print(result_table_Q2)
### Plot Results in box plot
Resilience_measures = c("Increase in felling volume", "Increasing share of uneven-aged
forests", "Increasing share of forests where clearcutting is performed",
  "Increasing share of forest area under protection", "Increasing people
employed within the forest value-chain", "Tightening criteria for forest certificates",
  "Increasing the share of mixed-species forests", "Increasing forest road
network density")
#The following function use also Q2_agg_arit/geom/eigen and mean_aggregated_CR_Q2
# Create a data frame
plot_data <- data.frame(
  Resilience_measures = Resilience_measures,
  Aggregated_Priorities = Q2_agg_arit
)
# Plot
#install.packages("ggplot2")
#library(ggplot2)
ggplot(plot_data, aes(x = Aggregated_Priorities, y = Resilience_measures)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", fill = "skyblue") +
  labs(title = "Priority Weights of Resilience Measures", x = "Aggregated Priorities", y =
NULL) +
  theme_minimal()

```